

NODAVLAT O'QUV MARKAZLARI TIZIMI PLATFORMASI UCHUN MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASINI YARATISH

Axmedova Zulxumor Ikromovna

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti

“Umumtexnik fanlar” kafedrası o'qituvchisi

axmedovazulxumor85@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10673163>

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining axborot-kommunikatsion va zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni ta'lim tizimiga joriy etishga bag'ishlangan Qaror, farmon va nutqlaridan kelib chiqib bugungi kunda ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalar, ma'lumotlar bazasi resurslari hamda dasturiy vositalarga bo'lgan ehtiyojning ortishi uni ishlab chiqarish va ta'limda qo'llash masalasi dolzarbligini ko'rsatadi. Ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimlarining umumiy tushunchalari, ularning turlari, klassifikatsiyasi, ma'lumotlar bazasining modellari va ularni me'yorlashtirish shakllari, ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan ishlaydigan tillarning komponentalari hamda so'rovlarni tashkil etish texnologiyasi, shuningdek bilimlar bazasi bilan ishlash tartibi xususida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Zamonaviy kompyuterlardan foydalangan holda yangi axborot texnologiyalari asosida ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash bilan akademik litsey va kasb-hunar kollejlari o'quvchilari, shuningdek, institut va universitet talabalari keng shug'ullanmoqdalar. Hozirgi kunda kompyuterdan foydalanuvchi har bir kishi WORD matn muharriri yordamida matnlarni qayta ishlashni, ya'ni kerakli ko'rinishda formatlashni, chop etishni va bir qancha nusxa olishni qiynalmasdan amalga oshiradi. Hisoblashlar bilan bog'liq masalalarni EXCELda, taqdimot jarayonlarini PowerPointda amalga oshirish ko'pchilikka ma'lum. Xuddi shuningdek, internet sahifalariga ma'lumotlarni kiritish uchun HTML tilidan yoki FrontPage programmasidan foydalanish kerakligini bilasiz. Kompyuter bilan bog'liq va kompyuter yordamida juda tez amalga oshirish mumkin bo'lgan shunday masalalar turkumi mavjudki, ular bilan har kuni va har qadamda ro'baro' bo'ladi. Bunday masalalar turkumi ma'lumotlar bazasi deb ataladi.

NODAVLAT O'QUV MARKAZLARI TIZIMI PLATFORMASI UCHUN MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASINI YARATISH

Hozirgi vaqtda o'quv jarayonini tashkil etishning ikkita asosiy shakli mavjud. Bu onlayn va oflayn o'rganishdir. Ushbu shaklni tanlashga, to'g'rirog'i, o'quv

markazi faoliyatida qaysi shakl ustun bo'lishi, uni tashkil etish va ishlash tamoyillariga bog'liq

Respublikamizda o'quv markazlarini tashkil etishdan asosiy maqsad – o'quvchi yoshlarga tanlangan soha bo'yicha maktabda olayotgan bilimlarini yanada mustahkamlash, hamda bilim saviyasini oshirishdir. Jamiyatda o'quv markazlari foydalanuvchini fan bo'yicha chuqur saviyaga ega bo'lishiga yordam beradi.

Buning ahamiyati shundaki, o'quv markazlari ish vaqti jarayoni o'quvchining vaqtiga mos xolda tanlashi, masofa jihatidan qulaylik, o'quvchilarning iqtidoriga mos holatda fanni tanlash imkoniyati, mustaqil o'z ustida ishlash imkoniyati va eng asosiysi – qisqa muddat ichida katta natijaga ega bo'lish imkoniyatlarini beradi.

Nodavlat o'quv markazlari tizimi platformasi uchun ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratishda SQL ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimidan foydalanildi va quyidagi jadvallar tayyorlandi:

1. Platforma foydalanuvchisi avvalo tizimda ro'yxatdan o'tishi zarur, chunki platforma foydalanuvchisining ma'lumotlar bazasi shakllantirilmasa, tizimdagi mavjud imkoniyatlardan foydalana olmaydi. Foydalanuvchining ma'lumotlar bazasida
2. 3-jadvalda ko'rsatilgan ma'lumotlar bazasi shakllantiriladi.

id	f_ismi	f_familiyasi	f_telefon_raqami	f_login	f_password
1	Faxriddin	Nuriddinov	*****	*****	*****
2	Hayitbek	Asrorov	*****	*****	*****
3	Mehroj	Amirqulov	*****	*****	*****
4	Yulduz	Shodiyeva	*****	*****	*****
...

3-jadval. Foydalanuvchining tizimda foydalanishi uchun zaruriy ma'lumotlarni o'zida saqlash imkoniyatini beruvchi jadval.

Foydalanuvchi ma'lumotlarini ma'lumotlar bazasida saqlash uchun quyidagi quyidagi API PHP dasturlash tilida yozildi:

```
<?php
    $host = "localhost";
    $user = "includei";
    $parol = "Y106M8etC[zIT*";
    $baza = "includei_doctor_database";
    header("Access-Control-Allow-Origin: *");
    header("Access-Control-Allow-Headers: *");
    header("Content-Type: application/json");
```



```

$json_str = file_get_contents('php://input');
$json_obj = json_decode($json_str);
$logink = $json_obj->login;
$password = $json_obj->password;
$user_name= $json_obj->user_name;
$user_phone= $json_obj-> user_phone;
$log= $json_obj->log;
$pas= $json_obj->pas;
$email= $json_obj->email;
if($logink = "*****" && $password = "*****") {
    $conn = mysqli_connect($host, $user, $parol, $baza);
    $sql = "INSERT INTO registration (user_name ,user_phone ,
login, password, email)
VALUES ('$user_name', '$user_phone', '$log', '$pas', '$email')";
    if (mysqli_query($conn, $sql)) {
        $success= array('success'=>'true');
        echo json_encode($success);
    }
} else {
    $failure = array('success'=>'false');
    echo json_encode($failure);
}
mysqli_close($conn);
?>

```

3. Platforma uchun o'quv markazlari va ular to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar shakllantirildi. O'quv markazlari to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarni platformaning ma'lumotlar bazasida 4-jadvalda ko'rsatilgan strukturada tayyorlandi.

id	m_nom i	m_manzili	m_telefon _raqami	m_login	m_passwor d	m_lon	m_lan
1	Include	Bux.sh., A.Somiy k., 23 uy	***** **	***** **	*****	*****	*****
2	Web interna tional	Bux.sh., Piridastgir k., 128 uy	***** **	***** ****	*****	*****	*****
3	ICity	Bux.sh., I.Mo'minov	***** **	*****	*****	*****	*****

		k., 3 uy					
...		

4-jadval. O'quv markazlarining zaruriy ma'lumotlarini o'zida saqlash imkoniyatini beruvchi jadval.

4. Platforma uchun o'quv markazlarida tahsil beradigan professor-o'qituvchilarning ma'lumotlar bazasi shakllantirildi. O'quv markazlarida tahsil beradigan professor-o'qituvchilarning to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarni platformaning ma'lumotlar bazasida 5-jadvalda ko'rsatilgan strukturada tayyorlandi.

id	id_marka	f_uqituvchi	f_uqituvchi	f_uqituvchi_otasinin
	z	_ismi	_famiyasi	g_nomi
1	1	Alibek	Shodmono	Nasullayevich
2	1	Urmzoq	Gaybullaye	Otabek o'g'li
3	1	Qodir	Aslonov	Ziyodullayevich
...

5-jadval. O'quv markazlarida tashil beradigan professor-o'qituvchilarning ma'lumotlarini o'zida saqlash imkoniyatini beruvchi jadval.

5. Platformaning o'quv markazlari tinglovchilari uchun tashkil qilingan fanlar majmuasining ma'lumotlar bazasi shakllantirildi. O'quv markazlarida tahsil beriladigan fanlar to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarni platformaning ma'lumotlar bazasida 6-jadvalda ko'rsatilgan strukturada tayyorlandi.

id	id_markaz	t_fan_nomi
1	1	Web dasturlash
2	1	Kompyuter savodxonligi
3	1	3d modeling
...

6-jadval. O'quv markazlarida tashkil qilingan fanlar majmuasi ma'lumotlarini o'zida saqlash imkoniyatini beruvchi jadval.

6. Platformaning o'quv markazlari foydalanuvchilar uchun tashkil qilingan fanlarning grafigi ma'lumotlar bazasi shakllantirildi. O'quv markazlarida tahsil beriladigan fanlar to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarni platformaning ma'lumotlar bazasida 7-jadvalda ko'rsatilgan strukturada tayyorlandi.

id	id_markaz	t_fan_id	t_uqituvchi_id	t_hafta_kuni	t_yaqt
----	-----------	----------	----------------	--------------	--------

SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

International scientific-online conference

1	1	2	3	Dushanba, Payshanba	13:00
2	1	1	1	Seshanba, Juma	13:00
3	1	3	2	Chorshanba, Shanba	13:00
...

7-jadval. O'quv markazlarida tashkil qilingan fanlarning grafigi ma'lumotlar bazasini o'zida saqlash imkoniyatini beruvchi jadval.

7. Platforma foydalanuvchilarining o'quv markazlarida tashkil qilingan fanlarga online registratsiyani amalga oshirish uchun mo'ljallangan ma'lumotlar bazasi shakllantirildi. Foydalanuvchilar o'quv markazlarida tashkil qilingan fanlarga online registratsiya ma'lumotlarni platformaning ma'lumotlar bazasida 8-jadvalda ko'rsatilgan strukturada tayyorlandi.

id	id_fan	id_t	if_f
1	2	1	1
...

8-jadval. O'quv markazlarida tashkil qilingan fanlarga online registratsiyadan o'tish ma'lumotlar bazasini o'zida saqlash imkoniyatini beruvchi jadval.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Axmedova, Z. I. (2024). LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IMKONIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 509-516.
2. STRUCTURES OF SMALL DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS
3. Z Akhmedova - Solution of social problems in management and ..., 2024
4. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). DATA BY COMBINING MAIL THROUGH TO SEND METHODS. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 198-207.
5. Akhmedova, Z., & Rahmatova, N. (2024). LMS (LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM) LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FEATURES. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 85-94.
6. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 106-116.
7. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). IPHONE OPERATIONAL IN THE SYSTEM MOBILE APPLICATIONS TO CREATE INTENDED PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENTS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 111-121.

8. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI BOSHQARISH TIZIMLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 40-49.
9. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 120-128.
10. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 305-309.
11. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 171-177.
12. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 274-280.
13. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(12), 781-787.
14. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.
15. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.
16. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
17. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
18. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
19. Latipova, S. (2024). YUQORI SINIF GEOMETRIYA MAVZUSINI O'QITISHDA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA METODLAR. SINKVEYN METODI, VENN DIAGRAMMASI METODLARI HAQIDA. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(3), 165-173.
20. Latipova, S. (2024, February). SAVOL-JAVOB METODI, BURCHAKLAR METODI, DEBAT (BAHS) METODLARI YORDAMIDA GEOMETRIYANI O'RGANISH. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 25-33).

21. Latipova, S., & Sharipova, M. (2024). KESIK PIRAMIDA MAVZUSIDA FOYDALANILADIGAN YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR. 6X6X6 METODI, BBB (BILARDIM, BILMOQCHIMAN, BILIB OLDIM) METODLARI HAQIDA. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(2), 40-48.
22. Latipova, S. (2024). 10-11 SINFLARDA STEREOOMETRIYA OQITISHNING ILMIY VA NAZARIY ASOSLARI. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(6), 27-35.
23. Latipova, S. (2024). HILFER HOSILASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 3(2), 122-130.
24. Latipova, S. (2024). HILFER MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALAR UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. Development and innovations in science, 3(2), 58-70.
25. Latipova, S. (2024). KESIK PIRAMIDA TUSHUNCHASI. KESIK PIRAMIDANING YON SIRTINI TOPISH FORMULALARI. Models and methods in modern science, 3(2), 58-71.
26. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In "Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
27. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO 'YICHA TO 'G 'RI MASALALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 375-382.
28. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(10), 13-23.
29. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 95-104.
30. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 117-124.
31. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 108-115.
32. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 122-130.

33. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 208-215.
34. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
35. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
36. Quvvatov, B. (2024). DIFFERENTIAL TENGLAMALAR VA AMALIY ECHIMLAR ORQALI MAXSUS MODELLARNI QURISH. Menejment va iqtisodiyotda ijtimoiy muammolarni hal qilish , 3 (1), 108-115.
37. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g', Q. (2023). SUN'IY NERV TIZIMLARIDAN MODELLASHDA FOYDALANISH. Fan va texnologiyaning ko'p tarmoqli jurnali , 3 (5), 269-273.
38. Behruz Ulug'bek og', Q. (2023). TEXNOLOGIYA VA TIBBIYOT: DINAMIK HAMKORLIK. Tadqiqot va ishlanmalar bo'yicha xalqaro multidisipliner jurnali , 10 (11).
39. Bobokulova, M. (2024). IN MEDICINE FROM ECHOPHRAPHY USE. Development and innovations in science, 3(1), 94-103.
40. Bobokulova, M. (2024). INTERPRETATION OF QUANTUM THEORY AND ITS ROLE IN NATURE. Models and methods in modern science, 3(1), 94-109.
41. Bobokulova, M. (2024, January). RADIO WAVE SURGERY. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 56-66).
42. Bobokulova, M. (2024). UNCERTAINTY IN THE HEISENBERG UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 80-96.
43. Bobokulova, M. (2024). BLOOD ROTATION OF THE SYSTEM PHYSICIST BASICS. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(1), 64-74.
44. Bobokulova, M. (2024). THE ROLE OF NANOTECHNOLOGY IN MODERN PHYSICS. Development and innovations in science, 3(1), 145-153.
45. Boboqulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.
46. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.

ITALY

SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

International scientific-online conference

ITALY

47. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.
48. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.
49. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.
50. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
51. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
52. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
53. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
54. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
55. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
56. Muradov, O. (2024, January). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 46-55).
57. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. Models and methods in modern science, 3(1), 84-93.
58. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(1), 54-63.
59. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD

TECHNOLOGIES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 16-27.

60. Sharipova, M. (2024). IN THE FORM OF AN UNBOUNDED PARALLELEPIPED IN THE FIELD NONLOCAL BORDERLINE CONDITIONAL LINEAR THE REVERSE IS THE CASE. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 105-116.

61. Sharipova, M. (2024). FUNCTIONAL SPACES. IN SHORT REFLECTION PRINCIPLE. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 131-142.

62. Sharipova, M. (2024). A IS CORRECT OF THE INTEGRAL TO THE ECONOMY APPLICATIONS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 116-125.

63. Sharipova, M. (2024). ASYMMETRY AND KURTOSIS COEFFICIENTS. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 216-225.

64. Sharipova, M. (2024). TWO MULTIPLE OF THE INTEGRAL APPLICATIONS. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(1), 135-140.

65. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 360-365.

66. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 137-141.

67. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 135-138.

68. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. International journal of sciarchers, 2(2), 101-103.

69. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.

70. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 102-110.

71. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).

72. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 106-113.

73. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 115-121.
74. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 50-56.
75. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 420–424.
76. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 425–429.
77. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 525–532.
78. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
79. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
80. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. World of Scientific news in Science, 1(2), 163-176.
81. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2024). KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 383-390.
82. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG–LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.
83. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
84. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 66-76.
85. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). GAMMA FUNKSIYA. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 391–399.

